

TOXICITY STUDY OF SEAWEEDS IN RAT

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ABSTRACT

Seaweeds has many beneficial effects and are rich in protein, minerals namely iron, iodine, calcium and phytonutrients which have been reported to act as antioxidants. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the safety of four seaweeds in male albino rats. In the acute study a single dose of 2000mg to 5000mg of the selected seaweeds were fed to rats weighing 110-130gms and post observed for 14 days. No treatment related death was observed and the maximal treatment dose estimated was 5000mg in rats. For the sub acute study only two seaweeds that were found to be safe at acute study were taken. In sub acute study male albino rats weighing 110-150g were dosed with 5000mg of selected two seaweeds in powdered form for a period of 60 days. The results showed no toxicological change in body weight, food and water consumption, blood parameters, organ weight and behaviour in treated rats. Thus the two selected seaweeds were considered to be safe in rats at 5000mg dose and the study was undertaken as per the guidelines of OECD. Hence seaweeds can be used as a safe food or pharmaceutical supplement to improve the health of the common population.

KEYWORDS: Seaweeds, Rats, Toxicity, Biochemical parameters, safety and Diet supplement

INTRODUCTION

Seaweeds contain treasures of benefits for human race and in recent years marine resources are tapped for various bioactive compounds, pharmaceuticals and nutraceutical compounds. In India, seaweeds grow abundantly along the coasts of TamilNadu, Gujarat Lakshadweep and Andaman and Nicobar Islands. Kaliaperumal (1997) stated that rich seaweed beds are found around Mumbai, Ratnagiri, Goa, Karwar, Varkala, Vizhinjam and Pulicat in Kerala, Gulf of Mannar in Tamil Nadu and Chilka in Orissa. Approximately 700 species of marine algae are found in the Indian coast. Consumption of seaweeds is not so popular despite of its abundance in Indian coasts. In India, seaweed consumption is negligible except in the preparation of porridge from *Gracilaria* sp. and *Acanthophora* sp. in coastal states of Kerala and Tamil Nadu. In India people consume seaweed indirectly in the form of phycocolloids added in chocolate, ice cream, jellies and as stabilisers in food products (Dhargalkar *et al.*, 2005).

The benefits of seaweeds are numerous and profound. Harvested in pure seawater, seaweeds can be considered as nature's most complete and balanced nutrient food source (Wood House, 2003). The natural antioxidants are a stable part of nutrition as they occur in almost all edible macro and micro algae plant products. Polyphenols are the most numerous group of antioxidant components, Recently, aquatic habitats have increasingly been shown to provide a rich source of natural bioactive compounds with hypocholesterolemia, anti inflammatory, antiviral, antineoplastic, antimicrobial and hypertensive properties (Hanaa, *et al.*, 2008).

Seaweeds offer a wide range of therapeutic possibilities both internally and externally. Eating unprocessed dried seaweeds can yield many healing benefits. Many physical ailments in humans can be regularly resolved with the simple addition of seaweeds to their respective diets. Though seaweeds are consumed extensively by Indonesians, Japanese and Koreans who have understood the nutritional properties, valuable health benefits of these seaweeds are yet to be completely exploited by Indians. It is reported that seaweeds like *Ulva lactuca*, *Ulva reticulata*, *Enteromorpha intestinalis*, *Acanthophora spicifera*, *Gracilaria edulis*, *Padina tetrastomatica* and *Sargassum wightii* are highly concentrated in the coastal belt of Gulf of Mannar, Rameswaram to Kanniyakumari, Tamil Nadu. Because they are dry when purchased, sea vegetables require soaking in water prior to use. Seaweeds do not absorb toxic amounts of any element. It provides hundreds of organic compounds and is synthetic-toxin free.

There are extensive studies on nutritional value of fresh water algae like spirulina but seaweeds are yet to be popularized and promoted. Seaweeds added in small amounts are power houses of nutrition. Thus the safety of seaweed was evaluated using animal model.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

TOXICOLOGICAL STUDIES OF SELECTED SEAWEEDS

The four seaweeds collected for the study namely *Ulva lactuca*, *Ulva reticulata*, *Acanthophora spicifera* and *Padina tetrastomatica* were subjected to acute toxicity and sub acute toxicity to select the minimum lethal dose and to rule out the effect of any toxins.

The tests were carried out based on the Organisation For Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD) guideline for testing of chemicals 410.423 (2001).

Acute Toxicity

Pre weighed quantity of seaweed powders 2000 and 5000mg of all the four selected seaweeds were separately well macerated in a mortar and pestle and a suspension was made in one percent carboxy methyl cellulose. Seaweed test sample for dosing was prepared fresh prior to each dosing.

The dosing started with 2000mg/kg weight of the rat and tested with an increment of 300mg and increased to 5000mg. If the rat died in any one dosing the next low level dose of the seaweeds was administered to the rats.

Procedure for Study

Four groups(7 rats in a group) of young eight week old healthy female rats weighing (110-150g) in a group of seven were taken for the study. A total of twenty eight rats were used for the administration of four seaweeds with the test compound at a dose level from 2000-5000mg/kg bodyweight after 18 hours of starvation. Initially one rat in the group was dosed with 2000mg/kg body weight and observed for clinical signs and the dose was increased up to 5000mg/kg body weight and the rat was observed again. If the rat is alive then the same dose was administered to the other two rats in the group and observed for clinical symptoms.

Animal House Condition

Animal house temperature was maintained between 19 -25⁰C and humidity 30 -70 percent. Temperature and humidity was measured daily .The facility was provided with 12 hour light and 12 hour dark. Standard poly propylene rat cages with stainless steel top grill were used to house the animals. The cages were autoclaved. Cleaned paddy husk was used as a bedding material. Animals were housed in cages containing not more than 2/cage. Food and water were supplied to the animals. Standard rat pellet feed supplied by Lipton India Ltd, Bangalore was given to the rats and filtrated water were provided to the rats.Both drinking water and feed were provided ad libitum except during pre dose fasting where only water was provided.

Animal Observation

Single dose of 2000mg/kg or 5000mg/ kg body weight was administered to the animals and observed on the seventh and 14th day. After administration, body weight, gross pathological examination, weight of liver and kidney were noted on the 14th day after necroscopy of the animal. Body weight for all the 14 days was observed. Behaviour of the animal was also noted from 30 minutes after dosing and thereafter, observed after 1,2,4 and 6 hour after dosing. Thereafter the animals were observed once in every 24 hours for 14 days.

From the results of the study only two species of green algae were safe at a level of 5000mg /kg body weight and these seaweeds were subjected to acute toxicity studies.

ACUTE TOXICITY

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Animal chosen for the study

Adult male albino rats of wistar strain weighing around 250-300g were obtained from the animal house of the Tamil Nadu Veterinary and Animal Sciences University, Chennai. The animals were kept in poly propylene cages (four in each cage) at an ambient temperature of 25±2⁰C and 55±65% relative humidity. A 12±1⁰C was maintained in the animal house till the animals adjusted to the laboratory conditions and were fed with commercially available rat chow (Hindustan Lever Ltd , Bangalore, India) and had free access to water. The

animals were divided into three groups, each group containing 6 animals. The animals were supplemented with a single dose of 5000mg/day of seaweeds orally for a period of 60 days.

The groups are as follows:

Group I : Vehicle control (distilled water)

Group II : Administered seaweed *Ulva lactuca*

Group III : Administered seaweed *Ulva reticulata*

Physical Changes

Morphological changes in the body of the treated animals were noticed everyday by careful visual observation to see any physical changes in the body like hair fall, necrosis, infection, overgrowth and overall activeness of the animals. The control group and experimental group animals were weighed every morning with the use of a balance. The changes in the body weight were noted. The feed consumed, water intake and excreta quantity of all the group animals were measured everyday by standard techniques using measuring cylinder and balance (Sartorius).

Biochemical Analysis

The major hematological and biochemical parameters, mineral and enzymes were analysed. The biochemical tests were carried out using the serum sample. The details are given in Table 1

TABLE -1: METHODS USED FOR ANALYSIS OF BIOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS

Biochemical test	Biochemical parameters
Hematological parameters	Haemoglobin(g/dl)Cyanmethemoglobin method Ferritin(mg/dl),iron(mcg/dl), red blood cells(x10 ⁶ µl),platelets (x 10 ⁴ µl), white blood cells (x10 ³ µl), neutrophils(x10µl), lymphocytes (x10µl)(Raghuramalu <i>et al</i> ,2003)
Minerals	Sodium (mEq/L), potassium (mEq/L), chloride (mEq/L), phosphorus (mg/dl), calcium (mg/dl) and magnesium (mg/dl) (Raghuramalu <i>et al</i> ,2003)
Biochemical parameters	Glucose (mg/dl), cholesterol (mg/dl), total protein (g/dl), urea nitrogen (mg/dl), albumin (g/dl), globulin (g/dl)(Raghuramalu <i>et al</i> ,2003)
Enzymes	Alanine aminotransferase (u/l), Aspartate aminotransferase (u/l) and Alkaline phosphatase (u/l))(Raghuramalu <i>et al</i> ,2003)

The experiments were designed and conducted in accordance with the Institutional animal ethics committee number 1282/ac/09/CPCSEA.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ACUTE AND SUBACUTE TOXICITY RESULTS OF THE SELECTED SEAWEEDS

The four seaweeds collected for the study namely *Ulva lactuca* , *Ulva reticulata*, *Acanthophora spicifera* and *Padina tetrastomatica* were subjected to acute toxicity.

i. Acute Toxicity Results

Table -2 indicates the clinical sign of toxicity on administration of single dose of seaweeds orally to animals at 2000mg /kg body weight.

TABLE 2: OBSERVATIONS ON CLINICAL SIGNS OF TOXICITY AT 2000mg/kg BODY WEIGHT

Seaweeds	Observation on post dosing of seaweeds (N = 12)						
	0.5h	1h	2h	4h	6h	1-7 day	7-14 days
<i>Padina tetrastomatica</i>	ME	N	N	N	N	N	N
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
<i>Ulva reticulata</i>	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
<i>Acanthophora spicifera</i>	MD	N	N	N	N	N	N

ME – Mild Excitation, MD – Mild Depression, N - Normal

Among the selected seaweeds *Padina tetrastomatica* and *Acanthophora spicifera* had caused mild excitement in the animals, at 2000mg dosing, whereas the two green seaweeds *Ulva lactuca* and *Ulva reticulata* administered animals showed normal behavior and no clinical signs of toxicity. Similar results were obtained till the 14th day of observation pointing out the safety of using the above two seaweeds.

Observations on clinical signs of toxicity on dosing 5000mg/kg bodyweight of seaweeds are presented in Table-3.

TABLE -3: OBSERVATIONS ON CLINICAL SIGNS OF TOXICITY AT 5000mg/kg BODYWEIGHT

Seaweeds	Observation on post dosing of seaweeds at (N=12)						
	0.5h	1h	2h	4h	6h	1-7day	7-14 days
<i>Padina tetrastomatica</i>	MD	MD	MD	N	N	N	N
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
<i>Ulva reticulata</i>	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
<i>Acanthophora spicifera</i>	SD	MD	MD	N	N	N	N

SD – Severe Depression, MD – Mild Depression, N - Normal

Administration of seaweeds orally to animals at 5000mg/kg body weight showed that *Padina tetrastomatica* and *Acanthophora spicifera* had caused mild to severe depression in the animals during the first two hours and though the animals exhibited a normal behavior after this period these two seaweeds were not selected for further research. The two green seaweeds *Ulva lactuca* and *Ulva reticulata* treated animals showed normal behavior from initial dosing till the final day of observation. Hence green seaweeds were considered safe even at higher doses of 5000mg/kg body weight and therefore were used for further research.

The Table -4 shows the mean body weight of animals treated with the four seaweeds at 2000mg and 5000mg/kg body weight on the initial day, seventh day and fourteenth day after feeding.

TABLE 4: CHANGES IN BODY WEIGHT OF THE RATS ON FEEDING SEAWEEDS

Seaweeds	Mean body weight at 2000mg dosing			Weight gain (g)	Mean body weight at 5000mg/day			Weight gain (g)
	0 day	7 th day	14 th day		0 day	7 th day	14 th day	
<i>Padina tetrastomatica</i>	154.3	155.3	156.3	2	152	153	154	2
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	136.3	136.5	137	1	136	136	136.3	0.3
<i>Ulva reticulata</i>	121	121	121.2	0.2	120	120	120.4	0.4
<i>Acanthophora spicifera</i>	131.7	134.7	134.1	2.4	125.3	128.7	130	4.7

It is found from the results that animals fed with *Padina tetrastomatica* and *Acanthophora spicifera* gained an average weight of 2.4-4.7grams respectively on post dosing period of 0-14 days whereas only 0.2-1gram of weight gain at 2000 and 5000mg/kg body weight dosing levels respectively were observed for the two green seaweeds.

Gross pathology and mean organ weight of the rats at levels of dosing 2000 and 5000 mg/kg body weight of seaweeds are presented in Table-5.

TABLE -5: GROSS PATHOLOGY AND MEAN ORGAN WEIGHT OF RATS

Seaweeds	Gross pathology and Mean organ weight at 2000mg dosing			Gross pathology and Mean organ weight at 5000mg dosing		
	Gross pathology	Weight of liver	Weight of kidney	Gross pathology	Weight of Liver	Weight of kidney
<i>Padina tetrastomatica</i>	No lesions seen.	3.66	1.19	Petechial bleeding in liver and kidneys	3.54	1.14
<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	No gross lesions. Normal appearance	3.25	1.10	No gross lesions Normal appearance	3.25	1.11
<i>Ulva reticulata</i>	No gross lesions. Normal appearance	3.20	1.10	No gross lesions Normal appearance	3.20	1.09
<i>Acanthophora spicifera</i>	No lesions seen	3.95	1.16	Severe conjunction with hemorrhagic spots on liver	3.19	1.28

The results of the gross pathology and organ weight of animals indicates that *Padina tetrastomatica* and *Acanthophora spicifera* induced rats showed gross pathological changes and the organs showed considerable increase in their weights. In general the green seaweeds did not show any gross lesions in both the doses and the organ weights remained normal at the 14 day unlike *Padina tetrastomatica* and *Acanthophora spicifera* seaweeds.

From the results of the subacute study, it is inferred that the two seaweeds namely *Padina tetrastomatica* and *Acanthophora spicifera* are safe at dosing levels 2000mg/kg body weight and the two green seaweeds are safe even at dosing levels of 5000mg/kg body weight. The classification of the test items are based on the Global Harmonization System (GHS)(OECD,2001) for LD50 cutoff limits and are grouped under category 5. According to GHS, Category 5 is for chemicals which are of relatively low acute toxicity but which, under certain circumstances, may pose a hazard to vulnerable populations and Category 5 – Unclassified; LD50 \rightarrow 5000 [∞] requires no label requirements and hence was applied for *Ulva lactuca* and *Ulva reticulata* administration and further investigation.

ii. Sub Acute Toxicity Results

Ulva lactuca and *Ulva reticulata* were safe at 5000mg/kg body weight dosing and was taken for subacute toxicity studies by feeding the animals with 5000mg/kgbw of seaweed orally for a period of sixty days. The results of the study are as follows.

Table -6 indicates the physical changes observed in the animals after 60 days of supplementation with the two green seaweeds between the experiment and control group of rats.

TABLE -6: PHYSICAL CHANGES OBSERVED IN THE RATS

Physical changes	Control n=6	<i>Ulva lactuca</i> n=6	<i>Ulva reticulata</i> n=6
Weight	Slight increase	Slight increase	Slight increase
Physical activity	Active	Active	Active
Drinking	Normal	Normal	Normal
Food consumption	Normal	Normal	Normal
Body temperature	36.0 - 37.5°C	36.0 - 37.5°C	36.0 - 37.5°C
Respiratory rate	80-85 breaths/min	80-85 breaths/min	80-87
Food consumption	5-6 g/100 g body weight	5-6 g/100 g body weight	5-6 g/100 g body weight
Water consumption	7 - 9 ml/100 g body weight	8-10ml/100g body weight	8 - 10 ml/100 g body weight
Urine production Fecal production	4.5 - 6 ml/ body weight	5 - 6 ml/ body weight	5 - 6 ml/ body weight
	9 - 10 grams	10 - 12 grams	10-14grams
Urine pH	7.7	7.8	8.1
Urine specific gravity	1.04 - 1.07	1.04 - 1.07	1.04 - 1.06

The results of the study reveals that the animals in all the three groups showed slight increase in weight from the initial weight of 250-300g, were active, consumed food and water normally and had normal body temperature. The food consumption of all the three groups was 5-6g/100 g body weight. Water consumption was more in the seaweed supplemented groups (8-10 ml/100 g body weight) than the control group (7-9 ml/100g body weight) because of the high fibre content present in the seaweed.

Similar result was seen for urine and fecal output which may be due to the bulk or presence of algal polysaccharides in the seaweed. The urine pH ranged from 7.7-8.1 and *Ulva reticulata* supplemented rat had a higher pH of 8.1, probably due to the alkaline nature of seaweeds which when consumed decrease the acidity of the body. Specific gravity of urine was in the range of 1.04 -1.07 for all the three groups. The respiratory rate was found to be 80-85 breaths/min in all the three groups. From these results the normal physical pattern of the animals observed point out the non toxicity nature of the selected seaweeds at the administered level of dose and hence safe for human consumption.

Details of the Biochemical Parameters in the Animal Supplemented Group

The change in biochemical parameters were recorded after 60 days of supplementation of the selected green seaweeds (Table -7)

TABLE -7: HEMATOGRAM OF THE SEAWEED SUPPLEMENTED ANIMAL GROUP

Biochemical parameters	Mean hematological values n=6			
	Control n=6	<i>Ulva lactuca</i> n=6	<i>Ulva reticulata</i> n=6	Reference value
Serum ferritin (ng/dl)	111.33±3.21	119.0±3.60	131.67±2.08	20-220
Serum iron (cg/dl)	67.33±2.08	71.0±0.60	121.67±2.08	60-170
Red blood cells(x 10 ⁶ µl)	6.27±0.21	7.13±0.81	7.30±0.44	5.4-8.5
Haemoglobin (g/dl)	13.00±1.00	18.33±1.53	19.33±1.04	11 - 19
Platelets (x 10 ⁴ µl)	1.80±0.10	1.87±0.15	2.53±0.42	1.5 – 4.5
White blood cells (x 10 ³ µl)	5.40±0.26	3.97±0.15	6.63±0.55	3.7 – 4.9
Neutrophils (x 10µl)	5.53±0.35	5.73±0.45	7.70±0.26	4.0 - 10.2
Lymphocytes (x 10µl)	4.967±2.51	5.6±3.61	6.2±2.08	5.6-8.3

The results of the study revealed that all the parameters namely serum ferritin, serum iron, red blood cells, white blood cells and hemoglobin increased considerably in experimental groups treated with seaweeds than the control group. The total ferritin levels were comparatively high in seaweed administered animals with 119±3.60 and 131.67±2.08 as against 111.3±3.21 of control group. The serum iron increased in *Ulva reticulata* supplemented animals (121.67±2.08) than control and *Ulva lactuca* supplemented animals. This increase may be attributed to the iron content present in the seaweeds. Though there is an increase in the iron content the values are well within the normal range of 60-170mcg/dl.

Research studies have proved that marine algae species namely (*Ulva*, *Sargassum*, *Porphyra* and *Gracilariopsis*) combat iron deficiency and anemia. According to Maria *et al.*, (2009) reported that iron from algae are easily absorbed by the body.

The total red blood cell and white blood cell count was high in seaweed groups than in the control group. The hemoglobin levels were near normal in seaweed supplemented groups with 18.33±1.53 and 19.33±1.04g/dl. The increase in hemoglobin levels may be due to the presence of the high iron content in both the seaweeds with 45gm/100gm in *Ulva lactuca* and 56gms/100gms in *Ulva reticulata*.

The normal blood parameters seen in seaweed supplemented rats are a positive indication that these natural foods can be used as a diet supplement for combating iron deficiency anemia. Similar study conducted by Jothibai *et al.* (2009) revealed that *Ulva lactuca* supplemented animals showed an improved haematogram than the control.

Table -8 depicts the serum parameters of the rats supplemented with the green seaweeds and the control group.

TABLE -8: EFFECT OF ULVA LACTUCA AND ULVA RETICULATA EXTRACT ON THE BLOOD AND SERUM PARAMETERS IN RAT

Biochemical parameters	Mean biochemical values(n=6)			
	Control n=6	<i>Ulva lactuca</i> n=6	<i>Ulva reticulata</i> n=6	Reference values
Glucose(mg/dl)	120.00±5.00	108.33±3.51	112.67±5.03	85-132
Cholesterol(mg/dl)	65.67±3.06	66.33±1.52	67.67±2.52	46-92
Total protein(g/dl)	6.30±0.30	7.40±0.40	7.20±0.26	6.3-8.6
Urea nitrogen(mg/dl)	39.33±4.51	37.00±2.00	40.33±2.08	32-54
Albumin (gm/dl)	3.47±0.45	3.70±0.20	3.80±0.26	3.3-4.9
Globulin (gm/dl)	2.77±0.25	2.70±0.20	3.43±0.21	2.4-3.9
Sodium (mEq/L)	138.0±7.55	142.67±3.05	147.67±2.52	140-150
Potassium (mEq/L)	5.30±0.30	4.97±0.15	5.27±0.25	5.2-7.8
Chloride (mEq/L)	105.67±5.13	105.33±3.06	100.0±2.00	95-115
Phosphorus(mg/dl)	8.20±0.26	8.63±0.15	10.30±0.20	6.2-11.7
Calcium(mg/dl)	8.97±0.42	10.67±0.21	11.37±0.47	10.7-13.7
Magnesium(mg/dl)	2.13±0.15	2.87±0.15	3.13±0.151	2.6-3.11
Aspartate aminotransferase (U/L)/SGOT/AST	37.00±2.65	37.00±2.00	37.00±2.65	37-92
Alanine aminotransferase(U /L)S GPT/AST)	32.33±2.52	29.00±4.00	37.00±2.00	17-50
Alkaline phosphatase (U /L)	42.67±3.06	48.33±1.52	59.00±4.00	39-216

The glucose content of experimental animals showed a significant variation when compared against the control. The analysis of the data infers that majority of the parameters namely cholesterol, protein and albumin increased by 1-2% in *Ulva lactuca* and *Ulva reticulata* supplemented rats against the control group.

Similar result was seen for minerals like sodium, phosphorus, calcium and magnesium, which increased from control value. The increase in mineral content in *Ulva reticulata* and *lactuca* supplemented animals may be attributed to the high mineral content naturally present in the seaweeds. The increase in the blood parameters were well within the normal range. Whereas few parameters like urea nitrogen, globulin and chloride decreased in *Ulva lactuca* treated rats and increased in *Ulva reticulata* treated rats expect for chloride it had decreased. Thus it also found that there is a considerable variation between the two seaweeds on the blood parameters. The serum marker enzymes such as SGOT, SGPT and ALP were found to be within normal limits in both the seaweed supplemented groups. This result indicates that the selected two green seaweeds are safe for human consumption and do not indicate hepatotoxicity and liver damage. The elevated activities of SGOT and SGPT in serum are indicative of cellular leakage and loss of the functional integrity of cell membranes in liver (Drotman et al., 1978). In the present study the enzymes were in the normal range of 39-92U/L SGOT, 17-50U/L SGPT and ALP 39-216U/L in both the seaweed supplemented groups. Thus this normal blood picture projects the non toxic nature and the safe usage of seaweed.

CONCLUSION

The toxicological evaluation of the seaweed brings forth the fact that they are safe for human consumption at five gram levels and can be consumed up to ten gram everyday. Seaweed can go a long way to be used as a potential functional food. Seaweed has to be used as nature's wealth and harnessed in the right way to promote future health.

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A.Thahira Banu and S.Umamageswari: Continental J. Food Science and Technology 5 (2): 23 - 31, 2011

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Received for Publication: 23/08/2011

Accepted for Publication: 24/10/2011

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